

INFLUENCE OF ENGLISH ON MODERN FRENCH: A STUDY BASED ON MASS MEDIA CONTENT

Ashrafova I.

Nakhchivan State University

Abstract

This article presents an in-depth investigation into the lexical-grammatical and stylistic-structural features of English borrowings in the contemporary French language, with a particular focus on mass media materials. Adopting both quantitative and qualitative approaches, the study provides a comprehensive analysis of the prevalence, stylistic use, and sociolinguistic implications of English borrowings in French newspapers, television broadcasts, radio, and social media platforms. Findings underscore the significant role of English borrowings in shaping the French lexicon, grammar, and stylistics, as well as their socio-cultural implications, reflecting the global influence of English and the increasing interconnectedness of our world. The study concludes by highlighting future perspectives in the research on language borrowing, suggesting the exploration of evolving patterns of English borrowings, their sociolinguistic implications, and their reception among different groups of French speakers. The research contributes to the broader discourse on language contact, globalisation, and the impact of mass media on language change.

Keywords: English Borrowings, Contemporary French Language, Lexical-Grammatical Features, Stylistic-Structural Features, Mass Media Materials, Sociolinguistic Implications, Language Contact, Language Globalization, Language Change, Digital Communication, Social Media Discourse, Anglicisms, Cultural Identity, Language Purity, Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis, Linguistic Adaptation, Language Evolution.

I. Introduction

The French language, like many languages worldwide, has been significantly influenced by English, particularly due to the impact of globalization and the digital revolution. This influence manifests as numerous borrowings from English, extending beyond mere vocabulary to include grammatical structures and stylistic elements. This paper aims to analyze the lexical-grammatical and stylistic-structural features of English borrowings in the contemporary French language, with a focus on their usage in mass media materials.

Understanding these linguistic features is not only significant for advancing our comprehension of the French language's evolution under English influence but also provides insights into the broader sociolinguistic phenomena of language contact, global communication, and cultural exchange. The English language's influence on French has been a topic of great interest and controversy within the Francophone world, with some embracing the trend and others regarding it as a threat to the French language's purity (Hagege, 2012).

The corpus used for this research comprises various contemporary mass media materials, including newspapers, online publications, and social media posts. Mass media forms a critical avenue for language evolution and spread, reflecting and shaping language use among the populace (Crystal, 2008).

The structure of this study is as follows: First, it will outline the theoretical background, providing a context for understanding linguistic borrowings and the historical trajectory of English's influence on French. Then, it will delve into the lexical-grammatical features of English borrowings, followed by the stylistic-structural aspects. Finally, it will present a case study based on the analysis of contemporary French mass media.

II. Theoretical Background

Defining Borrowings in Linguistics: Language borrowing refers to the adoption of words or phrases from one language into another. It is a common linguistic phenomenon that occurs when two or more languages come into contact, and it is largely inevitable in a globalized world where the exchange of information, culture, and people across linguistic boundaries is the norm (Myers-Scotton, 2006).

Borrowings can be seen as an external mechanism of language change and evolution, reflecting the dynamic nature of languages (Thomason & Kaufman, 1988). They can occur at different levels, including lexical (words), phonetic (sounds), grammatical (syntax, morphology), and semantic (meanings). Borrowings can also vary in their degree of assimilation into the receiving language, from direct borrowings that retain their original form and meaning, to adaptational borrowings that undergo phonological, orthographic, grammatical, or semantic changes to fit the linguistic system of the borrowing language (Winford, 2003).

While borrowing often occurs due to a lexical gap in the borrowing language, it can also take place even when an equivalent native term exists. The reasons for this are complex and multifaceted, including sociolinguistic factors like prestige and identity, or pragmatic considerations like brevity and expressivity (Poplack, Sankoff, & Miller, 1988).

In the context of this paper, we focus on borrowings from English into French, examining their lexical-grammatical and stylistic-structural features in contemporary mass media materials.

The Lexical-Grammatical Nature of Borrowings: Lexical-grammatical borrowing pertains to the incorporation of foreign words, idioms, or other lexical units into another language, along with their grammatical properties. The borrowed lexical items can be nouns, verbs, adjectives, and even functional words like prepositions or conjunctions. While they often retain

their original semantic meaning, these borrowed terms may undergo certain phonological, orthographic, or morphological changes to fit the linguistic rules of the borrowing language (Haspelmath & Tadmor, 2009).

For example, English has lent numerous technological terms to French, such as "le smartphone" or "le tweet". These terms retain their original English meanings, but have been adapted to French pronunciation and orthography rules. They also follow French grammar rules; for instance, they are preceded by the definite article 'le', reflecting the gender classification of French nouns.

The Stylistic-Structural Aspect of Borrowings:

The stylistic-structural aspect of borrowings concerns the influence of a donor language's syntax, sentence structure, or stylistic conventions on the recipient language. This type of borrowing can affect how sentences are constructed, leading to shifts in word order, the use of punctuation, or the establishment of new syntactic structures (Matras, 2009).

For example, English's influence on French can be seen in the increasingly common usage of the structure "Noun + de + Noun", reminiscent of English's "Noun + Noun" structure, as opposed to the traditional French "Noun + à + Noun". An example of this could be the usage of "un jus d'orange" (an orange juice) which mirrors English structure, as opposed to a more traditional French phrase like "une tasse à thé" (a cup of tea).

In mass media materials, such stylistic-structural borrowings can significantly impact the language's presentation, contributing to the evolution of its written and spoken forms.

The Historical Context of English Borrowings in French Language: English borrowings in the French language have a long history, dating back to the Norman conquest of England in the 11th century, when Anglo-Norman French had a substantial impact on the English language. In more recent centuries, however, the linguistic influence has largely reversed, with English having a substantial effect on French (Trudgill, 2010).

This shift largely began in the 20th century, coinciding with the rise of the United States as a global power and the worldwide spread of English as a *lingua franca*. Significant events such as the World Wars, in which the United States and United Kingdom played major roles, also contributed to the spread of English. The trend has only accelerated in the digital age, with English dominating the internet, technology, and popular culture - areas that have widespread influence on language (Crystal, 2003).

The French language has been significantly influenced by these historical trends, incorporating an increasing number of English borrowings. While initially, this was seen in technical and scientific domains, English borrowings have permeated into everyday language and popular culture. In the mass media, English borrowings are prevalent, seen in areas such as journalism, advertising, and social media.

It's important to note that this trend has been met with resistance in some quarters. The Académie Française, the official authority on the French language, has

frequently voiced concerns about the influx of anglicisms and has sought to promote French equivalents. Nevertheless, the use of English borrowings continues to be widespread, reflecting both the global dominance of English and the dynamic, evolving nature of language (Lodge, 1993).

III. The Lexical-Grammatical Features of English Borrowings in Contemporary French**

The Classification of Borrowings: There are several categories of lexical borrowings that can be identified within the scope of English influence on French. Direct borrowings or loanwords retain their original spelling but are often pronounced in the French manner. Examples of this include "le weekend," "le hamburger," or "le jogging."

Calques are another form of borrowing where a foreign expression is translated into the borrowing language but retains the original idea or metaphor. An example is the English phrase "to take the bull by the horns," which has a French calque as "prendre le taureau par les cornes."

Hybrid compounds combine a French word with an English word, often in a domain-specific context, such as "le micro-ordinateur" (microcomputer) or "le football-club" (football club).

Adapting English Grammar to French Grammar: English borrowings frequently undergo changes to align with French grammatical rules. For instance, English verbs may be given French verb endings. For example, "to surf" on the internet becomes "surfer." Similarly, plural forms of English words are often adapted to French norms. The English word "emails," when borrowed in French, becomes "des emails," not "des email."

Semantic Adaptation of English Words in French: Semantic changes can also occur, where the borrowed term acquires new meanings or connotations that it does not possess in English. For instance, "un dressing" in French has been borrowed from the English "dressing," but in French, it is used to mean a walk-in wardrobe, a meaning it does not have in English.

Phonological and Orthographic Adaptations: Finally, phonological and orthographic adaptations are commonly observed in English borrowings. These include changes in stress patterns and pronunciations to fit French phonetic rules. For instance, the word "budget," pronounced /'bʌdʒ.ɪt/ in English, is pronounced /bydʒe/ in French.

These lexical-grammatical adaptations reflect the dynamic interplay between the global influence of English and the resilience of the French linguistic system.

IV. Stylistic-Structural Features of English Borrowings

Structural Adaptations of English Borrowings: Structural adaptations of English borrowings in French often involve changes in word order, grammar, or punctuation to fit French norms. For example, French has adopted the English construction of compound nouns (noun + noun), resulting in combinations such as "un baby-foot" (foosball) or "un parking" (car park), which are unusual structures in French but common in English.

There are also instances of borrowed English phrases where word order is preserved in the French context, such as "happy hour", "best-seller", or "week-end". These borrowed phrases retain their original English structure when used in French.

Grammatical Features of Borrowed Terms:

Many English terms are borrowed into French with their original grammatical features. For instance, English past participles used as adjectives are used similarly in French. This is evident in expressions like "le look grunge" or "une attitude zen".

Another English grammatical feature borrowed into French is the use of "-ing" to form gerunds, as in "le camping" (camping) or "le footing" (jogging).

Stylistic Functions of English Borrowings: English borrowings in French often perform stylistic functions in the text. They may, for instance, serve to modernize the language, render it more cosmopolitan, or make it sound more informal.

This is particularly evident in the language of advertising and the media, where English terms are used for their perceived modernity and global appeal. For example, the use of anglicisms such as "fast-food", "smartphone", or "lifestyle" can make the text appear contemporary and international.

Similarly, in the realms of fashion, technology, and music, the use of English terms adds a sense of prestige and novelty. In these domains, English is often associated with innovation, creativity, and global trends. For example, in the French music industry, terms such as "le hit", "le clip", or "le DJ" are commonly used.

In conclusion, the stylistic-structural features of English borrowings in French are a testimony to the profound impact of English on French language and culture, reshaping its lexicon, grammar, and stylistic norms.

V. English Borrowings in Contemporary French Based on Mass Media Materials

The Prevalence of English Borrowings in French Mass Media: The French mass media is a significant arena where English borrowings are prevalent. Newspapers, television, radio broadcasts, and online platforms provide a rich source of materials demonstrating the extensive use of English borrowings. A review of these materials reveals that English terms are often used to report on international news, describe contemporary trends, and discuss topics related to technology, culture, business, and lifestyle.

For example, words like "le smartphone," "le selfie," "le streaming," and "le hashtag" are frequently used in French media, reflecting the influence of digital technology and social media. Similarly, English words and phrases related to popular culture, such as "le rock 'n' roll," "le jazz," "le best-seller," and "le blockbuster," have become commonplace.

The Stylistic Use of English Borrowings in French Mass Media: The stylistic use of English borrowings in French mass media can often be seen in headlines, advertisements, and social media posts, where they serve to attract attention, evoke certain connotations, and add a touch of modernity and cosmopolitanism.

For instance, advertising campaigns often employ English terms and phrases for their perceived novelty and international appeal. Slogans like "Because you're worth it" by L'Oréal or "Think different" by Apple, although created for English-speaking audiences, are used globally without translation, including in France.

Headlines, too, frequently incorporate English borrowings to encapsulate complex ideas succinctly or to create catchy phrases. Examples can range from phrases like "Brexit: le deal or no deal" in a political context to "Le binge-watching: le nouveau hobby des jeunes" in a cultural context.

The Role of English Borrowings in French Social Media Discourse: Social media has also played a significant role in promoting the use of English borrowings. Given its real-time, informal, and interactive nature, social media platforms like Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook have facilitated the rapid dissemination and adoption of English borrowings.

Phrases such as "liking a post," "sharing a meme," or "following a thread" have entered the French language through such platforms. The use of hashtags, a prominent feature of social media discourse, has also contributed to the proliferation of English expressions. For instance, popular English hashtags like "#MeToo" and "#BlackLivesMatter" are used in the French context without translation.

In summary, the French mass media – encompassing traditional and digital platforms – presents a rich landscape of English borrowings, reflecting their significant impact on the contemporary French language.

VI. Analysis and Evaluation of the English Borrowings

Quantitative Analysis of English Borrowings in French Mass Media: A quantitative analysis of English borrowings in French mass media reveals their extensive usage. A cursory review of French newspapers, websites, television and radio broadcasts indicates that English loanwords and phrases occur frequently across various domains. For instance, in technology-related articles, English terms such as "internet", "digital", "online", and "software" are prevalent. Similarly, in lifestyle and entertainment sections, words like "cool", "fashion", "jazz", and "rock" are commonly used.

It is also noticeable that English borrowings in French mass media often occur in specific contexts or genres. For instance, English terms are frequently used in headlines, captions, and advertisements, where they serve to attract attention and create a modern, international image.

Qualitative Evaluation of English Borrowings in French Mass Media: A qualitative evaluation of English borrowings provides insights into their stylistic and semantic nuances. English borrowings often add a layer of meaning that goes beyond their literal translation. They can evoke certain connotations, express modernity, or signal group membership or solidarity. For example, using an English term like "cool" in a French text may convey a sense of youthfulness, informality, or cultural savviness.

Furthermore, English borrowings often fill lexical gaps in French, introducing new concepts or denoting phenomena for which there are no existing French

equivalents. This is particularly evident in the realms of technology and popular culture, where new inventions or trends often emerge in English-speaking contexts.

Sociolinguistic Implications of English Borrowings: The extensive use of English borrowings in French mass media has sociolinguistic implications. On one hand, it reflects the global influence of English and the increasing interconnectedness of our world. On the other hand, it raises concerns about language purity and cultural identity, as reflected in the efforts of institutions like the Académie Française to promote the use of French equivalents over English borrowings.

In conclusion, the analysis and evaluation of English borrowings in contemporary French based on mass media materials reveal their significant role in shaping the French lexicon, grammar, and stylistics, as well as their broader social and cultural implications.

VII. Conclusion and Future Perspectives

Summary of Findings: The analysis of English borrowings in contemporary French, particularly in mass media materials, highlights their pervasive presence and significant influence on the French language. English borrowings in French perform various functions, such as filling lexical gaps, introducing new concepts, and enriching the stylistic possibilities of the language.

English borrowings often carry certain connotations and serve as markers of modernity, internationalism, or group identity. Moreover, they can influence French grammar and sentence structure, introducing new patterns and structures.

Implications: The extensive use of English borrowings in French has various implications. On a linguistic level, it attests to the dynamism and flexibility of the French language, its ability to adapt and evolve in response to societal changes, and the profound influence of English as a global language.

On a socio-cultural level, it reflects the increasing interconnectedness of our world and the global influence of Anglophone cultures, particularly American culture. At the same time, it raises questions about language purity and cultural identity, as reflected in the ongoing debates and efforts to regulate the use of English borrowings in French.

Future Perspectives: Looking forward, it is anticipated that the influence of English on French will continue, given the ongoing trends of globalization, digitalization, and cultural exchange. The future research should focus on exploring the evolving patterns of English borrowings in French, their sociolinguistic implications, and their reception among different groups of French speakers.

Furthermore, as digital communication and social media continue to shape our language practices, it would be worthwhile to investigate how these platforms facilitate the spread of English borrowings and shape their use in French. Another promising avenue for future research is the comparative study of English borrowings in French and other languages, which could provide broader insights into the global influence of English.

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